

Excess Gibbs' energy of binary mixtures of hard sphere fluids

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Hard sphere model of Boublik-Mansoori-Carnahan-Starling-Leland (BMCSL) with Labowitz and Zomick's non-additivity corrections has been utilized to calculate excess Gibbs' energy (G^E) for toluene-cyclohexane and toluene-n-heptane systems over the entire compositions. The results are in excellent agreement with the experimental one.

The study of the properties of liquid mixtures is of both practical and theoretical interest. On one hand it enables engineers and chemists to obtain reliable data for design purposes and on the other, it provides physicists with information on the relation between the macroscopic properties of a mixture and characteristics of its constituents molecules. Using dynamic method Saez *et al.*¹ studied isothermal vapour-liquid equilibrium for toluene-n-heptane, toluene-cyclohexane and toluene-p-xylene systems. Applying Generalised van der Waals model and Lacombe-Sanchez² model, Saez. *et al.* also calculated excess Gibbs energy for these systems. But these models fail miserably in explaining the experimental data. It is our endeavour to use the hard sphere model of Boublik-Mansoori-Carnahan-Starling-Leland (BMCSL) (derived originally by Boublik³ and later by Mansoori-Carnahan-Starling and Leland⁴) to obtain the desired values of the experimental results of the parameters.

Theory :

When a hard sphere of diameter σ_0 is dissolved in a hard sphere fluid of diameter σ , the excess Gibbs energy of mixing (G^E) at a given temperature (T) is given by BMCSL^{3,4} model as

$$G^E = RT \left\{ d\eta \frac{[(-3d^2 + 3d + 3)\eta^2 + (6d^2 - 9d - 6)\eta - d^2 + 6d + 3]}{(1-\eta)^3} + (2d^3 - 3d + 1) \ln \left(\frac{1}{1-\eta} \right) \right\} \quad (1)$$

where $d = \sigma_0/\sigma$, the solute-solvent diameter ratio; η the packing fraction of the fluid given by $(\pi/6)\rho\sigma^3$ and ρ is the number density.

Eqn. (1) is exact in the low density limit ($\eta \rightarrow 0$) for all diameter ratios and in the small solute limit ($d \rightarrow 0$) at all densities. Applying the latter condition, i.e. $d \rightarrow 0$, eqn. (1) reduces to

$$G^E = RT \ln \left(\frac{1}{1-\eta} \right) \quad (2)$$

Since G^E must be zero in the pure state of fluid, G^E for a liquid mixture can be expressed as

$$G^E = x_1 x_2 RT \ln \left(\frac{1}{1-\eta_m} \right) \quad (3)$$

where x_1 and x_2 are the mole fractions of two components and η_m , the packing fraction in the presence of solute is given by

$$\eta_m = \left(\frac{\pi}{6} \right) \rho_m \sigma_m^3 \quad (4)$$

where ρ_m and σ_m are the number densities and hard sphere diameters of the binary mixture and are given by

$$\rho_m = (x_1 \rho_1 + x_2 \rho_2) \quad (5)$$

$$\text{and } \sigma_m = (x_1 \sigma_1 + x_2 \sigma_2) \quad (6)$$

Introducing Labowitz and Zomick^{5,6} non-additivity correction terms $\Delta\sigma$ in the hard sphere diameter model as

$$\sigma_m = (x_1 \sigma_1 + x_2 \sigma_2) + \Delta\sigma \quad (7)$$

where $\Delta\sigma$ has the dimension of σ .

According to Amotz and Herschbach⁷, $\Delta\sigma$ for a solution with solute at infinitely dilute solution with a mole fraction of 0.5 can be expressed as

$$\Delta\sigma = \sigma_1 \sigma_2 / (\sigma_1 + \sigma_2) \quad (8)$$

$\Delta\sigma$ for the whole composition range may be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\sigma &= \frac{\sigma_1 x_1 (1-x_1) \sigma_2 (1-x_1) x_1}{\sigma_1 + \sigma_2} + \frac{\sigma_2 x_1 (1-x_1) \sigma_1 x_1 (1-x_1)}{\sigma_2 + \sigma_1} \\ &= \frac{2\sigma_1 \sigma_2 (x_1 x_2)^2}{\sigma_1 + \sigma_2} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Results and Discussion

The model discussed in the previous section has been

applied for toluene–cyclohexane and toluene–*n*-heptane systems. Since toluene–*o*-xylene system has small values of G^E , it is not suitable for testing theoretical models. Since even small absolute discrepancies may lead to differences between the experimental and calculated values we have excluded it from our studies. We have used the parameters in Table 1 to calculate the excess Gibbs energy for the two

Table 1. σ and ρ values for pure components at 298 K

Component	σ^a Å	ρ^b g cm ⁻³
Toluene	5.40	0.8684
Cyclohexane	5.33	0.7872
<i>n</i> -Heptane	5.96	0.6809

^aRef. 8, ^bRef. 9.

Fig. 1. Excess Gibbs energy of toluene–cyclohexane system at 298 K : (●) calculated, (□) experimental.

Table 2. Calculated and experimental excess Gibbs energy (G^E) of mixtures at equimolar composition

System	G^E (J mol ⁻¹)		
	Calcd.	Ref. ¹	Expt. ¹
Toluene + cyclohexane	292.60	260.71	292.85
Toluene + <i>n</i> -heptane	300.60	264.00	292.19

systems at 298 K. Figs. 1 and 2 show the experimental and calculated values of G^E for different compositions of toluene–cyclohexane and toluene–*n*-heptane systems, respectively. Figs. 1 and 2 reveal that the model works very well

Fig. 2. Excess Gibbs energy of toluene–*n*-heptane system at 298 K : (●) calculated, (□) experimental.

over the entire composition range. Table 2 gives the values of the excess Gibbs energy for different systems at equimolar composition. Also included in the table are the values obtained by Lacombe-Sanchez model² (the best one obtained by Saez *et al.*²). This clearly indicates that this model is much superior to the models used by Saez *et al.*¹. From their studies Saez *et al.* concluded that shape factor must be effectively introduced into the model for better performance. In our model this has been indirectly incorporated by adding a term $\Delta\sigma$ in eqn. (7). Further work on this line is in progress.

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